

Lessons Learned from Analysis of GP Free-text Data (A Case Study on Depression)

Matúš Falis^{1,2}, Matthew Iveson¹, Samuel McInerney², Franz Gruber², Emily Ball¹,
Luke Daines², Heather Whalley¹, Arlene Casey²

¹ Centre for Clinical Brain Sciences, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, UK

² Usher Institute, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, UK

Introduction

Depression is a major cause of disability, affecting about 4.4% of the global population [1]. Most treatment is handled in primary care. During GP encounters the patient is assessed on their mood and relevant symptoms (e.g., sleep or appetite), their change compared to previous encounters, and response to antidepressants (including adverse reaction) with potential adjustment (dosage, switching to a different antidepressant). Encounters are recorded into hospital systems using structured Read codes (representing conditions or tests) and free-text data (allowing finer detail). Here we describe our experience in analysing GP data within a Secure Data Environment (SDE) in the context of depression as part of the AMBER project [2] including statistics from a sample of records of patients with depression, the outcomes of discussions with clinical experts, and we highlight the opportunities and issues around GP data. While our work focuses on depression, our findings may be relevant to other psychiatric conditions or general recording of illness and treatment in primary care.

Methods and Data

After being granted exceptional approval by NHS Lothian we have retrieved a sample of over 9,650,000 records related to approximately 14,500 patients (from over 100 GP practices in Lothian contributing to the SDE). Each record has a Read code and each patient had at least one record with a depression Read code. The Read codes were merged into a superclass based on belonging to: a depression phenotype defined by a set of 90 (<0.5% of the unique Read codes in the data) depression Read codes (*positives*); a set of generic Read codes, e.g., phone or in-person encounters (*neutrals*) which we perceive as undercoded; and any other Read code (*negatives*). About 82.7% of the records also contain free text. These have been further analysed quantitatively (size, n-gram counts, proportion of records with free text) and qualitatively (common patterns in text). Findings about free text and the context of depression were discussed with clinical professionals.

Results

The positive records make up 0.285% of the dataset, while 8.285% are underspecified neutrals and 91.43% were assigned a specific unrelated Read code (negatives). The proportion of records with text (Table 1) is quite high for neutrals – these lack specificity and hence the free text would be the only way of identifying relevance to a condition. Only 47.49% of the positives have free text – significantly lower than for negatives (81.82%) and all records (82.73%). Free text is significantly underutilised when a depression Read code is present.

Table 1. Proportion of records with free text given Read-code derived superclass

Superclass	Proportion of Records with Free Text
Positive	47.49%
Negative	81.82%
Neutral	97.11%
All	82.73%

Furthermore, ~50% of the positives with free text contain a single token. Of these 56% are the string '<c>', while others include context-extending descriptions for the Read code (e.g., "persistent"). The lengths of positive notes follow a big-head long-tail distribution (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Histograms of the note lengths for positive records. Left – a detail on the big head (length of up to 500 tokens). Right – the full view of distribution showing the long tail.

Primary care data further suffers from commonly occurring issues, e.g., abbreviations and linguistic errors (typos, grammar, etc.). Depression is treated over a long time period, and hence sequences within an episode rather than individual records should be considered. Notes may refer to previous encounters and patients may change GPs/practices over time.

Quantitative and qualitative results were presented to a group of ~20 clinical professionals with experience in recording treatment of depression in primary or secondary care. These professionals were also presented with model scenarios and engaged in discussion guided by questions about recording depression treatment. We have found the following: (1) Undercoding is highly prevalent – this comes from the interaction between the professional and the coding infrastructure – clinicians are aware of specific codes existing, but never use them. Sometimes errors are deliberately introduced while typing text to avoid automatic prompts to assign a code. (2) Infrastructure for reporting adverse drug events is mostly used for extreme reactions – the overwhelming majority is recorded in free text. (3) Recording length/detail differs significantly between primary and secondary care (the latter is much richer). (4) Primary and secondary care rarely use or report results of standard tests, such as the PHQ-9 questionnaire [3] (a score of the patient's depression – for tracking progress/response). PHQ-9 was stated to be more used by psychologists than psychiatrists.

Conclusion

In our analysis we found that while GPs play a significant role in the treatment of depression and the free text attached to Read codes can carry useful information, it is underutilised in records already coded as depression. This lack of free text is in stark contrast to non-depression-coded text. An important avenue to consider is the classification of neutrally-coded records as relevant or irrelevant to depression based on the free text (highly common in neutral encounters). Clinicians recognise that undercoding is a common phenomenon. Some of it is due to the design of the coding infrastructure. The length and quality of recording differs significantly between primary and secondary care and neither seem to use common metrics from depression literature and recommended by NICE guidelines [4], such as PHQ-9 (for tracking progress and response). Instead, this information is described in free text resulting in further natural language processing research questions and opportunities for application development for further depression research (e.g., the AMBER project).

Study context

This study has been conducted as part of the AMBER (Antidepressant Medications: Biology, Exposure & Response) [2] project funded by a Wellcome Trust Mental Health Award. This work uses data collected by the NHS as part of their provision of patient care and support. Following exceptional approval by NHS Lothian, the analysis was completed on an extract of patient data in a Secure Data Environment managed by the DataLoch service: a partnership of the University of Edinburgh and NHS Lothian. One goal of the overall programme of work is to develop a scalable process for DataLoch in which clinical free-text can be de-identified for potential use within approved research projects. The data used for our development project cannot be requested in its raw form.

References

1. World Health Organization. Depression and other common mental disorders: global health estimates.
2. AMBER: Antidepressant Medications: Biology, Exposure & Response [Internet]. [place unknown: publisher unknown]. [date unknown]. Available from:<https://www.kcl.ac.uk/research/amber-antidepressant-medications-biology-exposure-response>
3. Williams N. PHQ-9. Occupational medicine. 2014 Mar 1;64(2):139-40.
4. Depression in adults: treatment and management [Internet]. [place unknown: publisher unknown]. 2022 Jun 29. Available from:
<https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng222/chapter/Recommendations>